

A SYSTEMATIC MAPPING STUDY OF EGOVERNMENT INITIATIVE CORE ASPECTS

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Abstract

The importance of eGovernment applications has attracted considerable attention all over the world. This is due to the fact that eGovernment applications provide multiple benefits to its users, such as increased efficiency, transparency, and productivity at a lower cost. However the complexity and variety of the initiative infers the existence of a number of challenges to the domain, such as technical, financial, cultural, organizational, and social barriers. These issues lie in different areas or aspects such as in management, and implementation, etc., and delay the progress of eGovernment initiatives. Therefore, the issues that come in the way of eGovernment progress must be treated very carefully. In order to avoid eGovernment issues and unintended effects, the practitioners must put some additional effort and consider different primary perspectives and aspects of eGovernment projects. A number of researchers agree that eGovernment initiatives require an appropriate method to enhance project's quality and reliability, and need to identify core issues that hamper the progress. The researchers suggest that these issues can be identified and removed when few core aspects are considered and carried out effectively to achieve higher quality and more reliable eGovernment system. Many eGovernment studies exist for eGovernment challenges and about the importance of some important areas in eGovernment as separate topics. However, there is no comprehensive understanding of what key aspects should be considered and analyzed, what focus areas exist in these eGovernment aspects or how they enhance eGovernment activities. Therefore, to address this gap, we carried out a systematic mapping study using review protocol, to classify and to structure the research evidence that has been published in the eGovernment field and the focus areas reported by them. One hundred and thirty two (132) empirical studies have been quantitatively mapped to the classification schema. The major eGovernment aspects are identified as adoption, development, implementation, management, infrastructure, and stakeholders' importance. Several research gaps and vital eGovernment subjects for practitioners are identified. As an outcome, this study has produced a list of possible eGovernment aspects to be considered to move towards successful eGovernment initiatives.

INTRODUCTION

eGovernment importance has been realized around the globe and a number of countries are progressing towards

better eGovernment solutions (Abbas et al., 2011), ("UN Survey," n.d.). eGovernment refers to the use of

information and communication technologies (ICTs) to improve the public sector organizations' activities (Al-Shboul et al., 2014). The public sector activities have been defining the country's progress since more than a decade, providing huge benefits such as increased transparency, efficiency, accountability and service delivery at a reduced cost (Almarabeh and Abuali, 2010) and (Al-Shboul et al., 2014).

eGovernment projects currently are not only developed to provide services to the public sector, but target private sector as well (Mergel, 2016). As eGovernment have become mature and are implemented to assist in multiple important domains, they have not only become difficult to develop, but have also been hard to plan and execute (Anna and Kei, 2005), (Layne and Lee, 2001). Such varied and complex nature of eGovernment initiatives implies existence of several challenges ranging from organizational, cultural, and social issues to technical and financial issues (Elder & Garman, 2008) and (Mergel, 2016). Some of the issues are ICT infrastructure, security, lack management support, collaboration, lack of resources, training, digital divide, culture and high costs, etc.. These challenges exist in various areas, such as in implementation, management, etc., and hamper the progress of the initiative (Mergel, 2016). Therefore, these issues ought to be cautiously dealt with, so the intended goal of eGovernment initiatives could be achieved (Sharma (2014), Rangarirai et al., (2010), and Yildiz (2007).

A lot of research in eGovernment field has investigated the eGovernment results and the factors that may influence the eGovernment effectiveness (Heeks & Bailur (2007), (Almarabeh and Abuali, 2010), and Dada (2006) . Despite the fact it is crucial, existing research offers little insights into the multifaceted nuances (aspects) of eGovernment initiatives (Dada (2006) and (Heeks, 2003) . The practitioners must put some additional effort and consider different primary perspectives and aspects of eGovernment projects (Heeks, 2003). The eGovernment issues can be removed when the core aspects are known and the practice is carried out effectively to achieve higher quality and more reliable eGovernment system (Elder & Garman, 2008) and (Mergel, 2016). According to Heeks & Bailur (2007), there are a number of open research issues and subjects of eGovernment initiatives. One issue is that eGovernment projects are basically software projects, however differ from traditional software projects and

therefore require specific aspects to be considered. Many eGovernment studies exist for eGovernment challenges and about the importance of some important areas in eGovernment as separate topics (Anna and Kei, 2005), (Andersen, 2006) (Nograsedk, 2011), and (Gichoya, 2005). However, a comprehensive understanding of what key aspects should be considered and analyzed, what focus areas exist in these eGovernment aspects or how they enhance eGovernment activities is still limited and remains largely unexploited (Yildiz (2007) and Mergel, (2016). Therefore, in order to fill this gap, we carried out a systematic mapping study using review protocol, to classify and to structure the published research evidence in the eGovernment field and the focus areas reported by them.

The systematic mapping is a new research method in the software engineering field, adapted from other domains by Kitchenham and Charters (2007). This method is an alternate to systematic reviews, and is conducted when the amount of empirical data is less, or when the subject under investigation is too broad. The mapping study is conducted at the higher granularity level, aiming to provide overview of a field and to find research gaps for future research (Kitchenham and Charters (2007).

Systematic mapping studies have been conducted by a number of researchers on a number of topics using different methods or guidelines. A sample of those mapping studies is stated below with their research topics and guidelines used.

- Condori et al., (2009) conducted systematic mapping of the available research literature on software requirement specifications using guidelines by (Petersen et al., 2008) and Kitchenham and Charters (2007).
- Jalali and Wohlin (2012) provided map of literature on global software engineering using guidelines by (Petersen et al., 2008) and Kitchenham and Charters (2007).
- Barreiros et al., (2011) performed mapping of published literature focusing on software engineering test beds based on Kitchenham and Charters (2007) guidelines.
- Engstrom & Runeson (2011) conducted systematic mapping of available literature on software product line testing using guidelines by (Petersen et al., 2008).

- Barbosa & Alves (2011) conducted a mapping on software eco-systems using Kitchenham and Charters (2007) guidelines.
- Laguna & Crespo (2013) created systematic maps on the literature available on the software product line evolution based on the (Petersen et al., 2008) guidelines.
- Wnuk and Kollu (2016) provided systematic mapping of literature on requirements scoping constructed on the (Petersen et al., 2008) and Kitchenham and Charters (2007) guidelines.
- Penzenstadler et al., (2014) conducted the mapping of literature on software engineering for sustainability, used guidelines by (Petersen et al., 2008) and Kitchenham and Charters (2007).
- Zein et al., (2016) performed systematic mapping of available literature on mobile application testing techniques using (Petersen et al., 2008) and Kitchenham and Charters (2007) guidelines.

After going through three filtration stages, a total of 132 studies (see Appendix A for the list) was chosen for our mapping study. We provide the synthesis of available data (evidence) built on SIX (6) classification sub-categories: (i) adoption, (ii) development; (iii) implementation, (iv) management, (v) infrastructure, and (vi) stakeholders' participation/importance category. A number of research gaps have also been stated and discussed: there is a need to understand eGovernment aspects properly before starting system development; the real-world environments' research need to be conducted; specific management practices that can help to initiate and execute the eGovernment projects successfully; and comparative studies for execution of the eGovernment system.

The results of this mapping study provide evidences for future research directions for improving eGovernment practice by considering all relevant key aspects. It gives sound concern to major eGovernment aspects and its analysis, that would be quite promising direction to the eGovernment success. In addition, the study provides an improved conceptual and general understanding of eGovernment areas for academia. Moreover, it contributes to the real world eGovernment practices, giving eGovernment managers some awareness about the practical implications.

The remainder of this paper is structured as follows: Section 2 presents the motivation for this study. Section 3 provides our research contribution. Section 4

presents the overview of related work, and the comparison and contrast of our study. Section 5 defines our mapping study methodology, followed by presentation of results in Section 6. Section 7 provides discussion of the mapping study. Finally, Section 8 concludes the work and gives future directions, and section 9 provides the limitations of this research study.

1. Motivation

eGovernment field has progressed significantly with more than 18 years of a research span. This progress of eGovernment research has given several results in terms of eGovernment services, benefits, potentials, practices, methods, techniques and frameworks as have been reported in a number of relevant journals and conferences (Heeks, 2002). A huge quantity of research is in progress on various eGovernment topics. Any new researcher in this domain needs to gain a sound understanding of the current state of the eGovernment research, encompassing many trends, and to get the knowledge of the future research prospects in this domain. Very few studies are available in which researchers aggregated research studies of eGovernment particular areas. However, these attempts' had limited focus, lacked much empirical evidence (Heeks, 2003), and did not follow the proper methodology.

Moreover, the early literature on eGovernment did not give ample attention to important aspects Heeks & Bailur (2007), but this subject has been brought up afterwards, and substantial amount of work has been accomplished on a number of topics related to eGovernment aspects.

An effort to aggregate all the relevant eGovernment studies is required to present a state of the art of the field (Kitchenham and Charters, 2007). Therefore, a systematic mapping study that presents general analysis of the eGovernment major aspects, providing many trends, and hinting towards various research opportunities in it would be more contributing to the field. So, it motivated us to conduct an empirical study that reports "what has been done in terms of eGovernment research areas in this domain?"

Another motivation to conduct this mapping study is that only one mapping study on eGovernment is available previously, conducted by (Lofstedt, 2005). His study did not followed the systematic procedure to conduct the study. Additionally, the study did not differentiate the "research facets", "contribution factes"

and “major areas”. Our study is comprehensive and is analyzed in more depth and detail. Furthermore, the first study revealed only fewer eGovernment services and areas. As the domain is progressing day by day, this mapping study directs to more topics, allowing more conclusions to be drawn.

2. Research contribution

Motivated by a study on research directions for eGovernment initiatives Heeks (2003), a systematic mapping study is contributed to the field that follows the guidelines given by (Petersen et al., 2008). It defines more adequate research questions, using proper search string, and includes a number of publication foras (journals, conferences, societies and workshops) on the subjected domain. The study present the state of the art of eGovernment aspects, filtered a huge collection of research papers, and extracted data from eGovernment research conveying its aspects and focus areas to gain an overview of eGovernment broader aspects. Additionally, this mapping study present the trends and opportunities of the eGovernment field. This analysis will help the researchers and practitioners identify eGovernment, regarding major aspects, focus domains lacking ample research. It will assist and direct the researchers and practitioners to focus on the topics that need their attention. Moreover, the analysis and conclusion can be regarded to be of special importance for eGovernment managers.

3. Related work

In the process of the literature search, we found one informal mapping study and some informal reviews in the eGovernment domain. The mapping study presented by (Lofstedt, 2005) structures studies under e-service, e-security and interactions. However, the study had limited focus. Further, the study does not present a systematic mapping study. In comparison, our study is comprehensive as it emphasizes on numerous areas of concern such as, adoption, development, implementation, management, infrastructure and stakeholders. Moreover, our study follows a well-defined procedure and investigates important focus subjects of eGovernment such as planning, challenges, success factors, roles involved and policies. The details of identified literature reviews are given in subsequent paragraphs.

A study conducted by Heeks, (2003) provides the analysis of design-reality gaps in eGovernment. He states

that most of the eGovernment projects fail due to the design-reality gaps. The paper focuses on reviewing the issue of design-reality gaps and its seven dimensions along with the peculiarities of those dimensions. The study provides guideline to identify and address eGovernment project risks. A real-world case study was assessed using the design-reality gap approach to reduce risks in an eGovernment project, to depict the value of such gap in an improved way. The limitation of the study is that it presents an informal review of government failure types, and is not describing the gap reductions of the case comprehensively.

In another study by Wahid & Siffat (2014) discussion on the critical factors that are important to be considered at vendor’s end for success of an outsourced project is provided. The study identifies various critical success factors using a systematic literature review method for different sized organizations, such as knowledge sharing, quality management, time management, flexible contracts, etc. On the basis of the identified factors, the study intends to propose “Outsourcing Contract Management Model (OCMM)” that provides the vendor organization with the ease of making outsourced projects effectively and improving the customer-vendor relationship. The study used the SLR technique to carry out the work. The limitation of the study is that only few factors are considered.

Another study by Kunstelj & Mirko (2004) claims that eGovernment development studies fail to provide a true overall assessment; and neglect important areas. Such narrow attention to eGovernment has slowdown the development in most countries significantly. To address this issue, the study critically analyzes the development using four-stage model and proposes some new ways for improvements. According to the study, an integrated approach is required to influence eGovernment development in right direction. On the basis of the analysis, the authors contributed a general model to evaluate integrated services. The study used an informal review method to assess the eGovernment development. The study does not provide guidance for integrated services in broader context.

In another review study conducted by Rahimy (2016), research done on the adoption and dissemination of eGovernment system is discussed. In addition, the study states that benefits, social influence and external pressure are highly related to adopt eGovernment services. The awareness among users needs to be

enhanced to progress. The study also found some strategic and technical challenges that affect eGovernment development. The study contributes by identifying the e-Government business application types, and the degree of usage of those applications. An informal review of literature related to eGovernment development applications is performed. The study does not provide suggestions comprehensively, and is discussing business type only.

The study by Alshehri & Drew (2010) states that eGovernment execution is not easy. The study gives an thought-provoking overview of existing challenges in eGovernment development such as financial, social and organizational barriers. Among these, some of the issues are: "ICT infrastructure", "privacy", "security", "top management support", "collaboration", "lack of qualified staff", "lack of training", and "high cost", etc. Based on the literature, the study shows a number of related problems about eGovernment such as definition of eGovernment, execution stages, and eGovernment implementation advantages. The technique used by the study is a review of the available literature of eGovernment stages, the issues and benefits in implementation. The study does not follow proper protocol for review and lacks to provide a comprehensive list of issues that come in way of eGovernment.

In a study by Yildiz (2007), discusses the limitations in eGovernment literature. It critically analyzes the definitions and development stages of eGovernment concept. Moreover, the study discusses the limitations of the concept. It provides some methodological remedies to overcome limitations, such as (i) improved examination of the processes of eGovernment projects within complex environments, (ii) address the problem of eGovernment policies, and (iii) incorporate eGovernment concept strongly to public administration. A short and informal review of literature is conducted on the vagueness of eGovernment definitions, the complexity in development process and some limitations in eGovernment approaches. The study consists of a narrow description of eGovernment limitations and lacks major critical points.

Another study by Gichoya (2005) assessed few case studies from some countries (developed and developing both) to get a small sight of real world eGovernment challenges. The study offers an overview of current challenges in developing countries such as lack of

management support, system quality, infrastructure issue, and lack of skilled team and resources etc.. The study proposed a conceptual framework based on the literature and the case studies data, depicting some input and output variables that define the eGovernment success. A qualitative research approach based on case studies literature was used to identify and analyze information. The study was an informal literature review, and included only one developing country for preliminary study.

In a study by Dada (2006), describes the gaps and eGovernment failure types. The study uses the models discussed by Heeks, for categorizing the failure types and describes why so many initiatives in developing countries fail. The paper concludes with the description that the main reason for eGovernment failure in developing areas is the gap between the actual and the built system. The study classifies literature and adds to the subjected area with the fact that the practitioners must understand the context in which the eGovernment development is carried out. A literature review of eGovernment failure types and gaps in developing countries is conducted. The study presents an informal literature review and lacks several various important aspects.

We did not find any comprehensive and convincing work on systematic mapping in eGovernment domain in our initial efforts for the literature search, which encouraged us to conduct such an in-depth and formal mapping study. Additionally, we found a very few literature review studies, reporting on eGovernment field (e.g. Heeks, 2003, Gichoya, 2005, Dada, 2006, Rahimy, 2016), but none of them apply a rigorous formal method. The details of these review studies are presented in Table 1A and Table 1B.

This current study uses a systematic mapping approach to form a classification scheme, to find and investigate evidence for eGovernment aspects and the focus areas that have been available earlier, so that an extensive overview of empirical studies in eGovernment area can be provided. Investigating all related data for eGovernment important aspects and focus domains are therefore required, so that possible research gaps could be identified and supplementary work could be suggested, for example, systematic literature reviews. Table 2A and Table 2B present a comparison and contrast of these reviews with our study.

4. Research methodology for systematic mapping

This section defines the systematic mapping approach that has been used for this study. The details of plan and conduct of this review are described in this section as well.

Our systematic mapping research methodology for this study used the guidelines given by Petersen et al., (2008), and Kitchenham and Charters (2007). This systematic review is also stimulated by other systematic mapping studies (Barreiros et al., 2011, Engstrom & Runeson 2011, Barbosa & Alves 2011, Wnuk and Kollu 2016), specifically in the software engineering area. Such methodological review generally provides a large-grained overview for a domain, and helps to provide a starting point to recommend topics for future research Petersen et al., (2008).

According to Petersen et al., (2008), a systematic mapping method comprises of five (5) distinct stages; having process steps and outcomes (**Error! Reference source not found.**). The first stage defines research questions. The second stage conducts the search. At this stage, the search strategy is stated and primary studies are identified. The third stage involves paper screening. The key-wording of abstracts is done at fourth stage. At this stage, a classification scheme is constructed. The last stage is the data extraction and mapping procedure. In this stage, the relevant papers are mapped into the scheme based on the extracted data. The stages in this mapping practice might appear to be sequential; however, it is essential to be stated that few steps are iterative. For example, the classification scheme

develops and is updated all over the process as new terms are added or combined while reading the selected papers.

4.1. Research questions

In this mapping study, the classification scheme is created on the basis of all identified relevant data and knowledge added by studies reporting eGovernment and its core aspects. Moreover, the study intends to find focus areas and the research gaps to suggest what needs to be done for further research in future to extend the present body of knowledge. Therefore, we ought to determine the contributions of papers on eGovernment core aspects reported so far. As stressed by Heeks, (2003), it is essential to find the particularities of eGovernment domain due to its diverse nature and features. We concentrate this systematic mapping study on empirical studies on eGovernment domain core aspects and their focus subjects due to the deficiency of review studies in this area. To accomplish the above objectives, the following primary and sub-research questions (RQs) were stated:

Primary RQ: Which studies empirically investigate eGovernment initiative core aspects and their focus areas?

sub-RQ1: What research approaches are applied by the studies and which contribution facets they offer?

sub-RQ2: What type of study setting were used by these studies to investigate their required information?

sub-RQ3: Which publication fora included studies on eGovernment aspects?

Table 1A:-								
Comparison of Review Studies								
Study	Author	Review Type	Year	eGovernment component	Systematic Methodology followed	Study Purpose	Sample Size	Relevant Findings
E-Government-Assessment of current research and some proposals for future directions	Ulrica Lofstedt	Mapping Study	2005	Overview	To some extent	To determine the shortcomings, and suggest future research directions in eGovernment by conducting a review of literature and forming a map.	35 studies	eGovernment is not analyzed properly at the theoretical level. eGovernment must be considered with a notion of forming new perspectives to involve citizen in eGovernment and in use of e-Government services. The social context is also important for eGovernment success.
Most e-Government-for-Development Projects Fail How Can Risks be Reduced?	Richard Heeks	Literature Review	2003	Design-reality gaps	No	To provide a guide to identify and address risks for failure of eGovernment schemes by	40 government reports	The major cause of eGovernment failure is the lack of understanding the design-reality gaps and the costs that come in the way. There are multiple forms of these

						reviewing literature.		design-reality gaps. In order to reduce eGovernment failure, we need to understand all these design-reality gaps.
Factors influencing vendor's capability regarding offshore software outsourcing contract: a detail study using systematic literature review	Abdul Wahid Khan and Siffat Ullah Khan	Literature Review	2014	Vendor's perspective	To some extent	To identify critical success factors that are important for vendors to consider in outsourcing projects, for successful management and best execution of project by reviewing available literature.	133 studies	The outsourcing vendors can improve the vendor-client relationships by: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Providing quality services and products • Providing proper communication to mitigate risks (if any) • Providing proper top management support to sustain long lasting relationships
Evaluating the progress of e-government development: A critical analysis	Mateja Kunstelj and Mirko Vintar	Literature Review	2004	Development	No	To identify and define the areas that	9 approaches from European Union reports	The existing approaches to development have a narrow focus on eGovernment development.

						must be included within the integrated approach for eGovernment by reviewing literature. So progress could be made and strategic objectives could be achieved.		Additionally, they do not provide an overall view to form new development guidelines that could promote the development towards understanding the long term objectives. Monitoring metrics is quite helpful to guide about the eGovernment development.
The Potential Advantages of Implementing e-Government as well as Factors on Such Adoption	Salem A.S. AL-Rahimy	Literature Review	2016	Adoption	No	To find the factors determining the adoption of eGovernment, organizational performance in developing countries by conducting a review of literature	23 studies	There is a deficiency in empirical data regarding important factors influencing organizations to adopt eGovernment.

Table 1B:- Comparison of Review Studies								
Study	Author	Review Type	Year	eGovernment component	Systematic Methodology followed	Study Purpose	Sample Size	Relevant Findings
Implementation of e-Government: Advantages and Challenges	Mohammed Alshehri and Steve Drew	Literature Review	2010	Challenges	No	To assess the available literature regarding eGovernment stages of implementation, its challenges and benefits	30 studies	eGovernment includes many stages of development, and give multiple benefits to multiple government sectors, citizens and business. However, the eGovernment execution is not easy. It has to face a number of challenges and barriers which have to be treated very carefully.
E-Government research: Reviewing the Literature, limitations and ways forward	Mete Yildiz	Literature Review	2007	Challenges	No	To review the limitations in the eGovernment literature and provide	60 studies	In order to address the issues, the remedies suggested are: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Better examination and explanation of eGovernment processes

						suggestions regarding how to overcome those limitations		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Address the under-specification problem in the eGovernment literature by conducting more empirical studies • Adding eGovernment subject strongly to majority of public administration research
Factors Affecting the Successful Implementation of ICT Projects in Government	David Gichoya	Literature Review	2005	Challenges	No	To identify and synthesize characteristic challenges in developing countries by reviewing a sample of literature.	9 case studies	Developing nations are far behind in implementing eGovernment initiatives successfully. In order to improve their ICT projects, countries need to understand factors that play important role in eGovernment and its success.
The failure of E-Government in Developing Countries: A Literature Review	Danish Dada	Literature Review	2006	Design-reality gaps	No	To provide design-reality context overview using	25 studies	The practitioners must understand the context in which they are working,

							Heeks “archetypes of failures”, by reviewing some current literature.		in order to develop successful eGovernment initiative.

Table 2A:-

Comparison and Contrast of review studies and current study

	Study	Lofstedt, (2005)	Heeks, (2003)	Wahid & Siffat (2014)	Kunsterlj & Mirko (2004)	Rahimy (2016)	Alshehri & Drew (2010)	Yildiz (2007)	Gichoya (2005)	Dada (2006)	Current Study
Characteristic(s)											
Review Type		Mapping study	Literature review	Literature review	Literature review	Literature review	Literature review	Literature review	Literature review	Literature review	Mapping study
Systematic methodology followed		Partially	No	Partially	No	No	No	No	No	No	Yes
Collect information about a specific field of study		Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
Give recom		No	Yes	No	No	Partially	No	Yes	Yes	No	Yes

mandat ions for future researc h												
Establis h the context of a researc h proble m or topic adequat ely		No	Yes	Yes	Partiall y	Partiall y	Partiall y	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
Identify the main method ologies and researc h techniq ues used in a particul ar researc h study		No	No	No	No	No	No	No	No	No	No	Yes
Identify the researc h proble m properl y		Par tiall y	Partiall y	Yes	Yes	Yes	Partiall y	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
Aim to help in decisio n- making		Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes

in an industrial setting											
Aggregated and compared empirical studies		No	No	Partially	No	No	No	No	No	No	Yes
Find new methods for specific research topic or problem		Partially	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Partially	Yes

Table 2B:-

Comparison and Contrast of review studies and current study

	Study	Lofstedt, (2005)	Heeks, (2003)	Wahid & Siffat (2014)	Kunsterlj & Mirko (2004)	Rahimy (2016)	Alshehri & Drew (2010)	Yildiz (2007)	Gichoya (2005)	Dada (2006)	Current Study
Characteristic(s)											
Analyze the problem related to industry		Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes

Confirm the method for practicing the topic in the particular domain		No	Yes	Partially	Partially	Yes	Partially	Partially	Partially	Partially	Yes
Provide support for grounded theory		Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
Inform students, researchers, and research groups about the particular research topic		Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes

Primary audience		Practitioners and academicians	Practitioners and academicians	Practitioners	Practitioners and academicians						
Review context		Academic	Industrial	Academic	Academic	Academic	Academic	Academic	Academic + Industrial	Academic	Academic
Review results indicate better understanding about certain research field		Partially	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
Specify research limitations		No	No	No	No	No	No	No	No	No	Yes
Results applicable		Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes

to indus try											

Fig 1: The systematic mapping process

Table 3:-

Search strings piloted on IEEEExplore.

# try	Search string	Results returned
Try1	((eGovernment OR public sector) AND (application OR software OR project OR initiative) AND (services OR business process) AND (development OR expansion OR growth OR progress) AND (aspect OR topic OR subject OR area) AND (main OR major) AND (approach OR method))	452
Try2	((eGovernment) AND (application OR software OR project OR initiative) AND (service OR process) AND (approach OR procedure) AND (aspect OR topic OR subject OR area))	619
Try3	((("eGovernment initiative" OR "eGovernment project" OR "public service delivery") AND (development OR expansion OR growth OR progress) AND (core OR major OR vital) AND (method OR approach) AND (aspect OR topic OR subject OR area)))	824
Try4	((("eGovernment initiatives" OR "eGovernment projects" OR "eGovernment services") AND (development OR expansion OR growth OR progress) AND (core OR major OR vital OR main OR focus OR concern) AND (aspect OR topic OR subject OR domain OR area))))	900

4.2. Sources of evidence

We performed the current study using the accessible information sources given by our library. The major search process relied on the online databases that report the Computer Science and ICT literature.

These publication databases include: IEEE Xplore, ACM Digital Library, Web of Science, Springer Link, Science Direct, and Google Scholar.

4.3. Search strategy

The review comprised of empirical studies of qualitative methods. Such studies ought to be directly associated to eGovernment initiatives and projects. Kitchenham and Charters (2007) proposed approach to construct the search string was adopted:

- Synonyms and alternative keywords were searched.
- Boolean OR was used to include alternate synonyms and spellings.
- Boolean AND was used to connect major terms together.

The primary search took a number of attempts to build the proper search strings. It was due to the general term “aspect” and is related to multiple research domains such as business, social sciences, and other distinct work terms. For each try, the search string was assessed on the basis of the number of relevant returned studies to our subjected topic, i.e., eGovernment. Additionally, using the preliminary research review and experience, we took 10 studies to look at the quality of our search strings, as second criteria. Then, the selected final ‘search string’ was the one which returned most relevant and maximum number of results in this domain. For example, we excluded the Try2 search string (Table 3) because the results were not too appropriate to the subject of investigation in comparison to Try4 search string.

The search terms were primarily determined based on the research questions (see Table 3). The terms “eGovernment initiatives”, “aspects”, and “focus area” were the main terms. In addition, we combined additional terms, i.e. synonyms such as “domain”, “topic”, “major” and “concern” to create our search wider and to guarantee that we cover up to greater extent. Furthermore, the term “development” was particularly available in a number of current studies of eGovernment domain. It is due to the fact that the term development is one of the most convincing peculiarities of eGovernment initiatives (Heeks, 2003) and a significant number of studies discuss the development aspect and its peculiarity. Therefore, we merged the term “development” in the search string, in order to make sure that search results cover more appropriate studies. We used IEEExplore for piloting

search strings for the 15 formerly chosen studies. Search strings ought to be much stricter. Therefore, the search string of Try4 was selected in this systematic mapping study.

4.4. Study selection criteria

The major emphasis of this mapping study is to identify empirical qualitative studies in eGovernment field. Perry et al. (2000) stated that empirical studies can be of many types such as surveys, case studies, and literature analysis, and are not restricted to experiments only. In addition, empirical investigations generally include hypothesis formation, situation observation, data analysis and to draw conclusions. According to Fenton et al. (1994), empirical evaluation and data can help software engineering research domain to gain a systematic foundation. Hence, in review planning stage, selection criteria were defined appropriately, so that any bias can be avoided. We considered a study to be empirical if the work is supported by relevant assessment and data. The studies not having sufficient data or if they just present views short of any supporting evidence are excluded from this review.

As proposed by Kitchenham and Charters (2007), we piloted selection criteria on identified studies, and accordingly, refined and improved it. We used the inclusion criteria mentioned below in this mapping study:

- Studies ought to be related to eGovernment initiatives, aspects, and focus domains.
- Studies must have qualitative data.
- Studies are published from 2000 to 2016.
- Studies must be in English language.

The exclusion criteria to exclude inappropriate studies is as follows:

- Studies that does not specify the eGovernment field and its aspects.
- Studies presenting quantitative or statistical data.
- Studies that do not have supporting evidence.
- Studies those are unavailable in full form.

As outlined above, we strictly followed the criteria and included or excluded studies accordingly.

4.5. Study selection process

The search procedure applied on relevant databases depends on the new search feature offered by online

All selected studies passed through three filtration stages (shown in), making the selection process

databases. Using this feature, we applied the search string and found meta-data of studies. The search procedure was limited to, studies of the computer science domain. Such limitation was made due to the commonly used term aspect in multiple domains. The literature search covered studies published from 2000 to 2016.

iterative and incremental. Initial step was associated to search the database via search string. Then, we filtered resulting research papers were using paper’s title and abstract, in the first phase. The papers having titles and abstracts not relating to eGovernment initiatives were excluded in this step.

Fig 1: Selection Process

In the second phase, scrutiny and filtration of research papers was done based on reading introduction, method and conclusion. Then, from list of leftover studies of first phase, studies were left out either because of not being empirical, do not satisfy the ‘study selection criteria (Section 5.4), or when studies were duplicates. In case of duplicate studies (in second phase), i.e. similar study was present at different places, the complete version of the study was chosen. The last filtration stage included a complete and detailed reading of left over studies.

abstracts of that final list of papers, and observed concepts that better reflects the problem under investigation and the focus area of papers. The researcher read the introduction and conclusions of papers when the abstract was weak to provide convincing keywords.

4.6. Keywording of abstracts (classification scheme)

The keywording intends to minimize the required time to construct the classification scheme, and it makes sure that the existing studies are included using the applied scheme. The thematic analysis method was used, that helps to identify, analyze and report themes from the data (Braun and Clarke, 2006). Keywording technique was applied to the selected studies, involving two stages. At the first stage, the first author (main researcher) went through

At the second stage, the selected keywords from multiple studies were combined to understand the contribution and nature of papers on the basis of the thematic analysis method. This practice directed us to identify a set of themes (sub-categories) for the classification scheme. After selecting final keywords, they were grouped and used to create categories for the map.

A number of concepts arose during the first stage of keywording procedure. Those concepts reflected different problems and contributions of papers. For example, empowerment of people, service delivery, effective planning, public sector barriers, etc. A large number of notions resulted due to this exercise. Therefore, in the second stage the resulted notions were organized via the focus area of each study. The topics of eGovernment: “adoption”, “development”,

“implementation”, “management”, “infrastructure”, and “stakeholder importance/participation” were cautiously selected as some higher level concepts. These concepts were appropriate to our selected papers and turned out to be the main category in the final classification scheme. We will present the final classification scheme in Section 6.2.

4.7. Data extraction and mapping of studies

The purpose of this step was to plot included research papers in the resultant classification scheme, and to extract the appropriate information to answer the specified research questions, i.e. the selected papers were classified into the classification scheme. We inserted data into tables, and per year publication frequencies was calculated. The Mendeley citation management tool was used to collect and handle papers’ citations. It comprised of title, authors’ names, publication year, and source. In addition, data was extracted depending on the research questions. The data extracted consisted of contribution facets, the research approaches employed, focus area discussed in study, discussed aspects of eGovernment, methodology, and study setting (i.e. the study was conducted at an industrial or academic level). The extracted data was organized and entered in excel sheets. The identified classification scheme and the extracted data helped to understand and identify research gaps in a better way.

4.7.1. Validity control

The responsibility of the first author was to read and complete the mining procedure for all studies identified for this systematic mapping study. On the other hand, second and third authors provided a thorough feedback on the protocol of this study, in order to minimize possible bias (if any). The second author analyzed 10% of selected studies randomly on his own, to minimize the bias in selection and data extraction steps of the study. The comparison of outcomes was done at a meeting, and no anomalies appeared. The inter-rater agreement was not used, as our assessment meeting intended to agree on an absolute consent for the used sample.

5. Results

5.1. Search Results

It was obvious previously that looking for and identifying relevant studies for eGovernment main aspects require forming the search string carefully. As stated before as well, the term “aspect” has been used in multiple disciplines. Due to this, numerous attempts were made for piloting search strings and for comparing results with studies identified previously. However, we consider that our ‘search string’ is consistent as it includes the term “eGovernment core aspects” and almost all identified papers are classified under this term.

Table 4:-
Remaining studies after each filtration step

Online database	Search results	Phase1	Phase2
IEEE Xplore	900	98	48
ACM Digital Library	1220	90	20
Web of Science	1100	18	16
Springer Link	680	25	7
Science Direct	989	28	11
Google Scholar	2215	87	30
Total	7104	346	132

At first the initial search results were 7104 papers from all sources. Later, we applied three filtration steps as described in Section 5.5. The searched online databases, initial number of resultant studies, and the final studies after applying filtration steps (see) are shown in Table 4. A total of 132 studies was finally selected after the filtration stages and

inclusion/exclusion criteria (Appendix A1 lists selected studies).

Out of the 132 relevant studies, 48 (36.3%) were from IEEEExplore and 30 studies (22.7%) from Google Scholar, twenty (20) from ACM Digital Library, sixteen (16) studies from Web of Science, seven (7) from Springer Link, and eleven (11) studies from Science Direct. The per year publication

distribution of selected studies is presented in Fig 2. The identified research studies were developing quite differently over time.

5.2. Classification scheme

Our classification scheme encompass FOUR (4) major categories: (i) Structure of the aspect, theme, or evidence; (ii) Contribution facets; (iii) Objects involved in the study (i.e., the study setting in which study was performed); and (iv) Research facets. On the basis of thematic analysis, the studies were grouped into six topics (sub-categories): adoption, development, implementation, management, infrastructure, and stakeholders' importance/participation, in the first category. These themes were created by investigating the key aspect addressed by each study, as labelled in Section 5.6. It became quite apparent at the "keywording of abstracts" stage that these identified aspects are the main research areas under which, appropriate studies can be classified. Each study clearly falls under any one of the six eGovernment aspects.

The second classification adapted from Shahrokni and Feldt (2013), inspects the contribution facets. They suggest that the contribution facet criteria place the studies into particular contribution type, namely; *framework, model, metrics, evaluation and recommendations*, in our case. A framework refers to a comprehensive and in depth technique that have wide range purpose, and focus on numerous research questions and areas. In comparison, a model has a particular purpose and precise purpose or research question. Studies in which the researchers recommend ways for improvement are classified under recommendations category. Metrics on the

other hand have some set of important guidelines that ought to be followed in order to get success. Lastly contribution facet "evaluation" signifies studies that study, evaluate the data and concludes their analysis.

The third category of classification is "study setting involved in the study" which gives answer for **sub-RQ2** and signifies the industrial/academic/mixed scrutiny. In this criterion, **academic** setting represents the study, which has been conducted merely for the purpose of academia or a simple analysis of a particular topic. On the other hand, **industrial** represents the study that is conducted in the industry, such as a case study, survey or ethnography, etc. Additionally, **mixed** type involves the combination of both industrial and academic settings. We were interested to learn about the studies' context, to explore two characteristics: first, it is vital to assess how selected studies have analyzed the eGovernment domain and to what extent. The analysis and evaluation using real world examples can ensure trustworthiness and reliability of studies. Secondly, the fact that eGovernment is an evolving field, we consider that studies should define challenges and issues in real world, to understand how teams tackle such projects and initiatives currently. Such awareness will help to reveal real-world difficulties and their possible way out to resolve actual problems.

The fourth classification is the "research facet", stimulated from Petersen et al. (2008). In this category, we select the current types of research approaches, as recommended and stated by Wieringa et al. (2006):

Table 5:-
Studies under each topic (sub-category)

Category	Studies(S)	Total # studies
Adoption	S1, S7, S16, S37, S47, S76, S78, S79, S83, S87, S102, S106	12
Development	S2, S3,S5, S6, S9, S13, S19, S22, S24, S29, S30, S33, S34, S39, S40, S44, S49, S50, S52, S54, S56, S57, S61, S64, S65, S66, S73, S74, S75, S86, S89, S92, S93, S97, S99, S100, S101, S105, S107,S109, S111, S116, S120, S123, S124, S128, S129, S131	48
Implementation	S4, S8, S11, S14, S15, S36, S41, S43, S48, S51, S55, S58, S62, S70, S71, S80, S82, S84, S85, S95, S98, S103, S104, S108, S112, S113, S114, S115, S117, S118, S121, S122, S125, S126, S132	35
Management	S72, S88, S94, S127, S130	20
Infrastructure Stakeholder Participation/Importance	S20, S25, S26, S31, S42, S63, S81, S96, S119	9
	S12, S28, S32, S53, S77, S90, S91, S110	8

Fig 2: Studies per publication year

- **Validation Research:** Refers to novel techniques’ investigation that are not yet executed in practice, such as experiments. No validation study is present in our mapping study
- **Evaluation Research:** Refers to methods applied in practice, and some evaluation is done of that method. It tells how the method was implemented (solution implementation) and what are the benefits and drawbacks of such evaluation of implementation. Identifying industry problems come under this category.
- **Solution Proposal:** Refers to provide a solution to any problem. The solution either can be new or some major addition of a current technique..
- **Philosophical Papers:** The studies that draw a new way of observing existing work. It may include to structure the field in form of a conceptual framework or taxonomy.
- **Opinion Papers:** Refers to studies that state the personal opinion about something. It means that whether a particular technique is worthy or bad, or ways to improve that work.
- **Experience Papers:** Refers to the personal experience shared by the author. It tells how a task has been accomplished in practice.

5.3. Answering the research question

RQ: Which studies empirically investigates government initiative, core aspects and their focus areas?

The studies involved in the study were gathered and categorized using the classification scheme defined in Section 6.2. The major category to

structure the topic comprised of: adoption, development, implementation, management, infrastructure, and stakeholder importance/participation (sub-categories). These studies are with clear contribution of any type (mentioned above), and are discussed in detail in the next sections. Out of 132 studies, twelve (12) studies

were under eGovernment adoption, forty eight (48) studies under development aspect, thirty five (35) studies under implementation, twenty (20) studies under management aspect, nine (9) studies under infrastructure and eight (8) studies under stakeholder participation/importance topic. Table 5 exhibits the involved studies for all topics respectively. It is notable that maximum number of the studies available were of development aspect 36% (i.e. 48 out of 132).

5.3.1. Adoption aspect

According to Meijer, (2015), in the eGovernment perspective, adoption is represented in terms of user willingness to use eGovernment services. Additionally, and as explained by Rehman & Esichaikul (2011), the success of eGovernment relies on the fact to identify adoption related factors. As per the findings of this study, a few number of studies on adoption are available i.e. 12 out of 132 studies (see Table 5).

The study presented by Ebrahim & Zahir (2005) [S7] addresses the importance of appropriate planning for adoption of eGovernment services. They have given a framework that would help managers to identify technical and organizational needs and reduce barriers. Another contribution by

Zulfiqar et al., (2015) [S87] discusses criticality of eGovernment adoption. They have used the unified theory of acceptance and use of technology (UTAUT) model that inspect the influential components of the adoption and utilization of eGov services. The model encompasses five elements; “performance expectancy”, “effort expectancy”, “social influence”, “facilitating conditions”, and “behavioral intention”.

A recent study by Ahmad & Alam (2015) [S78] discusses the policy implications for adoption of eGovernment using UTAUT model. They provided a framework for both theoretical and policy eGovernment implications as well. The framework suggested that “performance level”, “ease of effort” and “social influence” had high impact on behavior of users.

A study by Yonazi et al., (2010) [S47], assessed the adoption issues in a country’s context. They used case study approach to investigate the adoptions of three eGovernment organizations. The study presented by Rehman & Esichaikul (2011) [S16] discusses eGovernment adoption factors. They proposed a model for eGovernment adoption after assessing the reviews from experts. The model consisted of following elements: “security and trust”, “e-readiness”, “design”, and “demographic factors”

Table 6:-
Further classification of adoption studies based on focus area

Studies(S)	Focus area
S7, S87	Planning
S1, S16, S37, S47, S76, S79, S83, S102, 106	Challenges
S78	Policies and Strategies

Another study by Gregor et al., (2010) [S1], stated that limited adoption of eGovernment services is a major challenge for eGovernment in Bangladesh. They used action research for this study and addressed the limited adoption problem in eGovernment. Inadequate knowledge about the nature of eGovernment initiatives was identified as the major reason for several other issues in the domain.

The study by Sharma (2014) [S37], discussed issues and benefits of eGovernment adoption through case study analysis. A study by Alraja et al., (2015) [S76], performed a survey and discussed factors affecting adoption of eGovernment services. In a study by Sulaiman et al., (2013) [S79], has identified factors that define adoption of eGovernment services and thus supporting the government organizations to know what is required to increase adoption rate.

A study by Alghamdi & Beloff (2016) [S83], proposed an eGovernment adoption and utilization model showing the factors that influence the adoption of eGovernment initiative. The model stated the importance of “perceived benefit”, “awareness”, “previous experience” and “regulation and policy” to be most important for successful adoption of eGovernment.

The empirical study by Meijer (2015) [S102], proposed a theoretical model highlighting (1) stages for innovation course, (2) government and citizen issues and (3) cultural and structural barriers to be crucial in eGovernment adoption.

Another study by Savoldelli et al., (2014) [S106], discussed the adoption barriers in eGovernment. They categorized the adoption issues which cause hurdles in eGovernment adoption to be technical, political, managerial and organizational barriers. The focus areas of adoption aspect with their respective studies can be seen in Table 6.

5.3.2. Development aspect

eGovernment development is the practice to use information technology to systematize both the internal operations and its external interactions with concerns Andersen & Henriksen (2006). We found 48 studies out of 132 that have reported evidence on development aspect of eGovernment (see Table 5).

A study by Kunstelj & Mirko (2004) [S49], describe the facets that must be included in the development of eGovernment projects, to simplify and achieve strategic objectives. Another study by Layne & Lee (2001) [S5], pointed out the need for proper development and its planning for evolutionary eGovernment phenomenon, based on technical, organizational and managerial feasibilities. A case study presented by Robin et al., (2010) [S34], discussed planning perspective for development for offshore outsourcing. They argued that strong client-vendor relationship deliver long-term success and value. Chakarbarty et al., (2008) [S30], discussed outsourcing development in context of “relationship quality” and “service quality”. The outsourcing development is further indicated by Wahid & Siffat (2014) [S29], in addition to few development barriers. A study by Samsudin et al., (2013) [S40], discussed eGovernment outsourcing development. They stated that cost, old IT systems and skills are

among top issues while developing eGovernment initiatives.

A study by Swapna (2012) [S52], discussed significance of eGovernment planning w.r.t. development using country’s context and shares significance of transparency in eGovernment. Cordella & Hesse (2010) [S64], shed light on the importance of interaction in developing better eGovernment initiatives. A longitudinal study was conducted by Nasim & Ghufuran (2010) [S75], to explore challenges in eGovernment development, such as ICT infrastructure, Low ICT Literacy, workforce, collaboration, resistance handling and top management commitment issues considered as critical ones. Bakry et al., (2016) [S86], introduced an approach for the assessment of basic principles for eGovernment planning, its benefits, and steps for the development of principles. Another study by Reddick & Turner (2012) [S97], examined public service delivery and channel choice for development, comparing eGovernment to traditional service delivery. They emphasized the importance of planning to provide multiple contact channels for citizens, ensuring constancy of service response and information across channels.

A study by Batini et al., (2009) [S120], discussed the importance of proper planning and unique vision for eGov project development. They gave a methodology that had four phases: (1) “state reconstruction”, (2) “quality assessment”, (3) “new quality targets definition”, and (4) “preliminary operational planning”. They assessed the effectiveness of the methodology using a case study. Another study by Nour et al., (2008) [S124], emphasized the necessity of core values of eGovernment development. They proposed a framework consisting of two main factors i.e. point of eGovernment readiness and the level of democratization, helpful for making better development plans. A study by Ma et al., (2005) [S129], shared the fact that chinese eGovernment initiatives can be used as support to economic development, through a transparent and decentralized administration, helpful in economic development. A study by Reddick (2004) [S97], described the importance of development phases using relationship of government-citizen (G2C),

government-business (G2B), and government-government (G2G).

A study by Elkadi (2013) [S66], identified the critical factors relative importance in development of eGovernment using case study analysis, and suggested way to defined practices. Another study by Napitupulu & Sensuse (2014) [S73] synthesized selected studies to develop a generic model of success factor for eGovernment using Meta-Ethnography.

A study by Gregor & Imran (2005) [S2], proposed a multi-level framework for the strategies to advance ICT development in developing countries through

meta-analysis technique. The framework emphasized the importance of adequate knowledge. Another study by Anna & Alfred (2005) [S3], stated the significance of eGovernment effective development policies using case study analysis of Kiosk development projects. A study by Aichholzer & Schmutzer (2000) [S22], discussed major organizational strategies and their issues faced in initiatives to eGovernment development. Dawes (2002) [S50], shared an experience report stating the importance of eGovernment policy and strategies for effective development.

Table 7:-

Further classification of development studies based on focus area

Studies(S)	Focus area
S5, S29, S30, S34, S40, S49, S52, S64, S75, S86, S97, S120, S124, S129, S131	Planning
S66, S73	Success
S9, S13, S19, S24, S39, S57, S61, S74, S92, S100, S111	Challenges
S2, S3, S22, S33, S44, S50, S54, S56, S65, S89, S93, S99, S101, S105, S109, S123	Policies and Strategies
S6, S107, S116, S128	Roles

Another study by Lowery (2002) [S54], emphasized the improvement of an eGovernment strategy that must include exploring eGovernment market place, procedures to support eGovernment and re-engineering processes for development aspect. A framework was proposed in a study by Fang (2002) [S56]. The framework was given for analysis of challenges/problems in eGovernment development w.r.t. policy implementation. A study by Hee (2007) [S65], categorized the development stages of a country's eGovernment and analyzed the factors applied to establish vision and project objectives. Heeks & Bailur (2007) [S89], gave analysis of eGovernment development and holes for strategies. They gave recommendations as well. A study by Kaisara & Pather (2011) [S93], emphasized to have effective policies for service quality enhancement in development aspect of eGovernment. A study by Oza (2006) [S33], stated that development aspect in eGovernment ought to have integrated policies to handle outsourcing challenges. Mullen & Horner (2004) [S44] claimed that eGovernment lacks fully developed rules and models. They proposed a

framework to make better and defined eGovernment development strategies.

A study by Goldkuhl (2016) [S99] stated that eGovernment development need to have appropriate policies, they must be determined and defined in time. He proposed a model that consist theorizing, analysis of policy and work & evaluation phases for eGovernment development. Cordella & Tempini (2015) [S101] advised that bureaucracy plays vital role in eGovernment development and its improvement. Another study by Wu (2014) [S105] conducted comparative case study regarding rules and policies used in eGovernment development. He stated that traditional administration guidelines, directives for program and the national context are important while developing development strategies. Kromidha (2012) [S109] conducted comparative analysis and perceived that "global aid on strategic initiatives" for eGovernment and "benchmarking" are vibrant for development aspect. A study by Mukabeta et al., (2008) [S123] stated that basic requirements and priorities must be understood in order to define eGovernment development policies.

A study by Larsson & Gronlund (2016) [S100] argued that notion of “sustainability” is one of the main issues in eGovernment development. A study reported by Bhuiyan (2011) [S111] stated that digital divide, human resources, infrastructure and few social and political issues were critical challenges that caused eGovernment failure w.r.t. development aspect. Signore et al., (2005) [S9] discussed eGovernment challenges w.r.t the four stage model development, covering technical, economic and social categories. A study by Ramon & Pardo (2005) [S13] discussed eGovernment challenges and used selected review of current literature to create a framework for the eGovernment development aspect and its analysis. Walsham & Sahay (2006) [S24] discussed the current development challenges and future prospects for eGovernment. Persson et al. (2006) [S39] described challenges in one-stop government e-service development using reviews from inter-organizational concepts from the industry/business. Ulf & Karin (2007) [S57] analyzed success vs failure of two inter-organizational e-service projects through case studies. Al-Azri et al., (2010) [S61] discussed eGovernment challenges w.r.t. three paradigms namely, organizational, technology and end-users paradigm. A study by Wan et al., (2015) [S74] used a comparative analysis to discuss the importance of issues in eGovernment and eParticipation for development aspects. Joseph (2013) [S92] presented a theoretical model. The model encompasses technical, behavioral and political elements to be included for eGovernment development.

An experience report by Noor et al., (2014) [S6] described importance of main stakeholders in the development aspect of any eGovernment project. They explained the triangle of stakeholders’ i.e. executive agency, vendor and client. A study by Roiste (2013) [S107] conducted a case study and showed that identification of relevant stakeholder and their requirements are crucial to be understood in eGovernment development. Another study by Ching & Luk (2009) [S116] pinpointed the importance of leadership (stakeholder role) in the development aspect of eGovernment initiative in order to be successful. A study by Andersen & Henriksen (2006) [S128] used “Layne and Lee model for development” as a basis. They proposed “Public

Sector Process Rebuilding” (PPR) model, which is an extension of Layne and Lee model. The model aimed to increase the required actions and involved stakeholders in development of eGovernment initiative. The focus areas of development aspect with their respective studies can be seen in Table 7.

5.3.3. Implementation aspect

In eGovernment implementation, the notion refers to the act of execution of plan Paul and Thompson (2003). On the basis of data extraction, thirty five (35) out of 132 studies were specifically associated to implementation aspect of eGovernment, (see Table 5).

The first study conducted by Huang & Bwoma (2003) [S41] provided a comprehensive review of eGovernment practice and the fundamental planning that directly or indirectly impact government’s technology and implementation. Another study by Yadav & Singh (2012) [S58] reviewed the trends of current eGovernment technology and proposed a framework that included “open source” and “cloud computing” in implementation aspect of eGovernment. A study by Schuppan (2009) [S121] discusses the importance of integrated implementation approach concerned with context. He stated that such approach is more beneficial for successful eGovernment implementation. A study by Tseng et al., (2008) [S122] emphasized the procedure of decision making in implementation aspect of eGovernment. A study by Chan et al., (2008) [S125] gave the viewpoint of the numerous events in the implementation of eGovernment using an informational analysis of various eGovernment initiatives in a region’s context.

A framework proposed by Almarabeh & Abuali (2010) [S36] addressed challenges and prospects for implementing a successful eGovernment, and discussed factors to achieve eGovernment success. A study by Naimat et al., (2013) [S70] reported the critical success factors (CSFs) that could outgrowth success of eGovernment initiatives in terms of implementation aspect. Ten important CSFs were identified, using content analysis to assess interviews’ data. Another study by Ondego & Christopher (2016) [S82] used DeLone and McLean Information Systems Success Model to assess the success of eGovernment project implementation. Guha &

Chakrabarti (2014) [S103] argued that eGovernment and its implementation is viewed as network to assess the success factors, e.g. “politics of partner selection”, “achievement of goals”, “institutionalization process”, “system structuring”. Chen (2012) [S108] identified factors for successful implementation using case study of “eXtensible Business Reporting Language” XBRL. Political support and resource input was considered vital that helps in achieving project goals effectively. Shari & Manian (2010) [S114] conducted survey to gauge the success factors for eGovernment implementation. Some of those were clear agreement, experienced personnel, political determination and clear vision.

A study by Wilson (2014) [S104] described that eGovernment standard reflect strategies for implementation used in a country. He identified faster service provision, information access and issues of privacy to be considered during policy making and implementation. Tsai et al., (2009) [S117] proposed an approach based upon the analysis of ‘technology enactment framework,’ and ‘systems development

life cycle’ approach for better policy in eGovernment implementation. A study by Kim et al., (2009) [S118] used “OPEN” (“Online Procedures ENhancement for civil application”) system to assess the importance of policies in eGovernment implementation and showed that strong leadership is effective for successful implementation. Jeong et al., (2007) [S126] identified that better configuration of technology and business developments, resource utilization and stakeholders’ faith are useful to implement eGovernment successfully. A study by Paul & Thompson (2003) [S8] stated the importance of defined policies and strategies for eGovernment implementation. Another study by Huang & Farn (2016) [S85] proposed an action program/guideline for eGovernment to improve implementation of “Information Security Management Standardization (ISMS)” performance. A study by Azad & Faraj (2009) [S95] proposed a framework to enhance policies and strategies mechanism for eGovernment implementation. The framework emphasized the eGovernment “institutionalizing”.

Table 8:-

Further classification of implementation studies based on focus area

Studies(S)	Focus area
S41, S58, S121, S122, S125	Planning
S36, S70, S71, S82, S103, S108, S114	Success
S4, S11, S14, S15, S43, S48, S51, S55, S62, S80, S84, S98, S112, S113, S115, S132	Challenges
S8, S85, S95, S104, S117, S118, S126	Policies and Strategies

A study by Alshehri & Drew (2010) [S98] identified implementation eGovernment challenges as technical, social, financial and organizational issues. Another study by Ferro & Sorrentino (2010) [S112] argued that there exist several issues at organizational and technical level that must be understood and dealt effectively to get a successful eGovernment implementation. A study by Rose & Grant (2010) [S113] proposed a conceptual framework consisting of “client emphasis” to be critical in implementation for eGovernment success. Nagi & Hamdan (2009) [S115] identified eGovernment challenges in a country’s context; the main issues in eGovernment implementation were digital gap, lack of policies, lack of resources and application and illiteracy. A

study by Sarrayrih & Sriram (2015) [S132] offered a framework that emphasized the importance of clear vision and mission, literacy, infrastructure and training while implementing eGovernment project. Another study by Al-Shboul et al., (2014) [S51] examined and identified factors which affect the use of eGovernment in developing countries. They investigated the barriers and challenges which need to be addressed to implement eGovernment successfully. A study by Gichoya (2005) [S15] described the challenges that nations face while implementing government projects. Another study by Al-Rashidi (2010) [S14] discussed issues in eGovernment implementation and proposed a synthesized model for successful eGovernment

project implementation. The model cater issues such as; resistance to change, technical aspects, training issue, etc.

A study by Rangarirai et al., (2010) [S4] identified issues inhibiting the successful implementation of eGovernment. Another study by Yildiz (2007) [S11] provided the limitations of implementing eGovernment and shared the future directions accordingly. A study by Al-Moalla & Li (2010) [S43] shared the importance of e-procurement for successful implementation. A case study conducted by Sharma et al., (2014) [S48] described the analysis of eGovernment challenges in implementation.

A study by Chen et al., (2006) [S55] proposed an implementation framework for developing countries after analyzing eGovernment implementation in developed and developing countries both. The framework considered “infrastructure”, “resource utilization”, and “IT support” to be significant for eGovernment implementation. A study by Rahul & Sandeep (2010) [S62] analyzed a case of a failed eGovernment implementation in the developing

country’s context and identified challenges of implementation. A study by Bilal et al., (2011) [S80] identified eGovernment implementation barriers using a country’s context. Another study by Al-Rahimy (2016) [S84] also explored the eGovernment implementation strategic and technical challenges. The focus areas of implementation aspect with their respective studies can be seen in Table 8.

5.3.4. Management aspect

We found twenty (20) studies under the management category. The studies can be seen in Table 5.

A study by Nawi & Ibrahim (2012) [S17] shared the importance of management’s key dimensions that must be considered for effective eGovernment management aspect. Another study by Abbas et al., (2011) [S27] emphasized the importance of effective management and removal of its barriers. A study by Veen (2015) [S59] discussed importance of eGovernment planning in management perspective, shared a guideline to improve management practices.

Table 9:-

Further classification of management studies based on focus area

Studies(S)	Focus area
S17, S27, S35, S59, S68, S69	Planning
S18, S23, S72	Success
S21, S45, S46, S127	Challenges
S10, S38, S60, S67, S88, S94, S130	Policies and Strategies

A study by Kuhn et al., (2009) [S68] reviewed importance of planning in management perspective and proposed a generic guide for eGovernment projects. A study by Too & Weaver (2014) [S69] pinpointed same, the importance of effective management planning + proposed a framework. The given framework was concerned with the improvement of four features; “portfolio management”, “project sponsorship”, “project management office (PMO)”, “projects and program support”. Another study by Clemons (2000) [S35] discussed the importance of effective planning w.r.t. vendor relationship management, value creation and the role of senior management.

A case study by Krishna & Walsham (2007) [S18] identified the key areas that ought to be addressed

effectively for project’s success. A study by Chen & Perry (2003) [S23] proposed framework w.r.t external and internal factors for key management strategies for successful eGovernment system. Salem et al., (2013) [S72] identified critical success factors that influence change management using the survey method.

Another study by Heeks (2003) [S21] emphasized the challenges that occur due to “design actuality gaps”, basic cause for failure is ineffective management aspect. A study by Lee & Kim (2007) [S127] identified eGovernment challenges w.r.t management. They stated that financial, organizational and technical issues usually inhibit successful eGovernment. Another study by Andersen (2006) [S45] identified the eGovernment

management challenges as well. A study by Mundy & Musa (2010) [S46] proposed a framework to handle challenges effectively and to make mature eGovernment. The framework considered “policy implication” to be included at all levels of eGovernment.

A study by Ndou (2004) [S10] gave a detailed analysis for the need of better policies w.r.t management opportunities. Another study by Dawes et al., (2004) [S130] stated few dimensions such as “users”, “uses”, “organizational capabilities”, “data characteristics”, and “technology” need to be understood and explored effectively by management. A study by Hossain et al., (2011) [S38] proposed a framework for management influencing organizational eGovernment system; the framework shared guideline for organization’s integration. Another study by Nogrsek (2011) [S60] proposed a model for making effective strategies w.r.t. change management.

A study by Furlong (2014) [S67] highlighted the importance of proper policies & strategies for project management. A study by Mergel (2016) [S88] proposed a framework for management policies and strategies. The framework had three main principles; software “open by default”, “agile leadership approach” and “alternative contracting and outsourcing approaches” to be included. A study by Demetrios et al., (2011) [S94] did an analysis of eGovernment in country’s context and proposed a framework for management strategies & practices; suggested political, lawful, and financial cases to be significant. The focus areas of management aspect with their respective studies can be seen in Table 9.

5.3.5. Infrastructure aspect

Infrastructure refers to the structure required for proper working Bekkers (2009). We identified nine (9) studies, that can be classified in this category, see Table 5.

A study by Hossain et al., (2007) [S25] assessed current level of infrastructure of eGovernment initiatives in country’s context using survey and identified the factors for eGovernment’s success. Another study by Nkwe (2012) [S63] did same i.e. addressed the challenges and opportunities for developing countries. A study by Nam (2014) [S96] analyzed the eGovernment infrastructure usage and its elements using survey method.

Table 10:-

Further classification of infrastructure studies based on focus area

Studies(S)	Focus area
S25, S63, S96	Success
S20, S26, S31, S42	Challenges
S81, S119	Policies and Strategies

Another study by Bekkers (2009) [S119] emphasized the fact that flexibility is necessary while creating policies and strategies for infrastructures of eGovernment initiatives. He further stated that success cannot be achieved by assessing the technological perspective only; rather it needs political and legal values as well. A study by Yamin & Rawan (2016) [S81] stated that government policies are vital, and affect the success and failures of infrastructure.

A study by Shaukat et al., (2009) [S20] discussed problems faced by companies for defining infrastructure for eGovernment sector. Another study by Dada (2006) [S26] identified “design-reality gaps” a major cause of failed infrastructure and eGovernment failure. A study Chen (2003) [S31] proposed a framework for handling challenges in eGovernment. The framework emphasized the information technology role to manage networks for public decision-making and services for better infrastructure. A study by Hwang et al., (2004) [S42] gave a proposal of classification scheme to focus on infrastructure challenges and obstacles in eGovernment. The focus areas of infrastructure

aspect with their respective studies can be seen in Table 10.

5.3.6. Stakeholder participation/importance aspect

It is highly acknowledged that a number of stakeholders and groups play significant role in eGovernment, confirming the long-term success of the eGovernment Wang & Chen (2012). We identified eight (8) studies under this category (see Table 5).

A study by Wang & Chen (2012) [S110] stated that stakeholder importance and their participation is mandatory in creation of eGovernment policies and strategies in order to accomplish successful system. Another study by Herath & Kishore (2010) [S32] discussed offshore challenges and proposed a framework for its solutions. The framework showed that “vendor selection”, “vendor management”, “strategic decisions” and “effective management” are vital for better eGovernment services. Another study by Akman et al., (2005) [S91] identified citizen perspective and stated that gender and education issues cause eGovernment failure.

Table 11:-

Further classification of stakeholder importance/participation studies based on focus area

Studies(S)	Focus area
S32, S91	Challenges
S110	Policies and Strategies
S12, S28, S53, S77, S90	Roles

Another study by Rowley (2011) [S12] emphasized stakeholders' roles and benefits. She proposed a typology for key roles using stakeholder benefit analysis tool (SBAT) that analyzed stakeholders and their benefits. An additional study by Goldkuhl (2008) [S28] described importance of clients' along with the distinction of client and customer in eGovernment. A study by Tan et al., (2005) [S53] also described the importance of stakeholder for success. Another study by Verdegem & Verleye (2009) [S90] emphasized the importance of citizens participation in eGovernment. They proposed recommendations accordingly. Haider et al., (2014) [S77] proposed a model that stated “users’ importance” and “user-satisfaction” to be considered throughout eGovernment project. The focus areas of

stakeholder aspect with their respective studies can be seen in Table 11.

5.4. Research approaches and contribution facets

Sub-RQ1: What research approaches are applied by these studies and what contribution facets they offer?

Contribution facets of this mapping study were classified into metrics, evaluations, models, recommendations and frameworks, as shown in Table 12. Metrics is the type of contribution that provides some set of important guidelines that ought to be followed in order to get success. An evaluation refers to an assessment or evaluation of some information. The model has a particular goal and research question. The example of a model is the one given by Batini et al. (2009) [S120] for eGovernment planning. The recommendations represent specific ways of improvements in a particular domain. An example of recommendation is the one presented by Bhuyian (2011) [S111] that is based on eGovernment benefits and issues. Finally, a framework is a comprehensive and detailed technique having a extensive aim and focus on several research questions and areas.

We found twenty three (23) studies presenting frameworks for eGovernment initiatives ([S7], [S13], [S15], [S23], [S31], [S32], [S36], [S38], [S42], [S44], [S46], [S55], [S56], [S58], [S69], [S83], [S88], [S94], [S95], [S102], [S110], [S113], [S124]). In our mapping study, we found that most of the contributions facets (72 out of 132, 54%) were provided as evaluation type. On the other hand, contribution facet in terms of metrics and recommendations was the least studied (10 studies each). **Error! Reference source not found.** depicts the distribution of contribution facets, whereas Table 12 presents contribution facet for each study.

Research approaches can be summarized in Table 13. Most of the studies were conducted using the evaluation research approach (45 studies; 34 %). Comparitvely, the number of studies under experience papers category quite small (3%). Therefore, this necessitates more experience studies, that can help to know about the real world scenarios. Further, Table 14 presents a summary of research method that has been used by the authors of selected studies.

A map presenting papers' count of our major category against research approach facets is shown in Error! Reference source not found.. There is a lack

of eGovernment studies offering experience papers in all categories (see Fig. 5).

Fig 3: Contribution Facets

	Research	Papers	Proposal	Papers	erience Papers
Adoption	3	5	2	1	1
Development	22	4	7	13	2
Implementation	11	5	4	15	
Management	5	8	2	5	
Infrastructure	3	1		4	1
Stakeholders' Importance/Participation	1	2	3	2	

Fig 4: Map for main categories against research facets

Table 12:-

Contribution facet for each study

Types of contribution facet	Studies(S)	Description
Metrics	S1	Proposed the design decision principles for better evaluation and design in terms of eGovernment adoption.
	S59	Designed guidelines using the "HERMES" project management method for public sector projects.

	S68	Generated generic guidelines for project management in terms of auditing eGovernment projects.
	S84	Provided suggestions to overwhelm the consequences of eGovernment difficulties.
	S85	An action program approach for improved information security management systems (ISMS) is proposed.
	S86	Introduced an approach for the eGovernment initiative assessment involving basic principles and steps.
	S114	Provided suggestions to implement eGovernment development projects successfully.
	S122	Identified important lessons and provided recommendations to cater the managerial issues in the workplace
	S125	Suggested guidelines by integrating some vital components and eGovernment Implementation Frameworks, in order to organize and coordinate, plan and strategize eGovernment initiatives.
	S126	Suggestions provided to improve the adoption and institutionalization of eGovernment initiatives
Evaluation	S2	Survey done using data from several countries. Factors affecting progress of eGov strategies and trends were identified that were common to many countries.
	S3	Importance and challenges of kiosk development is being described w.r.t Government policies using two case studies of Kiosk projects.
	S4	Factors inhibiting the successful implementation of eGovernment in the Western Cape, South Africa were identified. Such as project fragmentation, leadership, perceived value of Information Technology, task co-ordination, and citizen inclusion, etc.
	S6	Finds that each stakeholder in eGovernment project has their own objectives, and had to face corresponding problems while achieving the objectives. A case study was taken for analysis.
	S8	Presents findings on designing and implementing eGovernment projects, considering policy, including regulatory issues, economic issues, and the rights of users.
	S9	Describes eGovernment challenges w.r.t the four stage model (cataloguing, transaction, vertical and horizontal integration), as well as from technical, economic and social perspective.
	S10	Describes the fact that there is a need for eGovernment restructuring, making the policies and procedures satisfactory for eGovernment success.
	S11	Analyses and presents the topology for eGovernment along with the limitations in implementing eGovernment.
	S17	Project failure classification is done according to ITPOSMO factor model, having seven dimensions, i.e. information, technology, processes, objectives, staffing and skills, management systems and structures, and other resources.
	S18	Describes eGovernment success factors i terms of different contexts, such as National Context, Provincial Political Context, The Provincial Internal Context, and Government

Organizational Context.

- S21 The concept of design-reality gap is specified using ITPOSMO factor model.
- S22 Investigates the major organizational challenges and gives guiding principles to overcome failure.
- S24 Surveys the available literature of information systems in developing countries regarding the key challenges, comprising of the technology role and the theoretical approaches.
- S25 Identifies some critical eGovernment success factors using survey, and states that absence of those factors causes failure.
- S26 Investigates that the main cause for eGovernment failure in developing countries are the Design-Reality Gaps: Hardware/Software Gaps, Private Public Gaps, Country Context gaps.
- S27 Describe the importance of PM practices implemented by the Electronic Government Directorate (EGD), a public sector entity under the Ministry of IT. A case study of EGD was taken for analysis.
- S28 Describes the importance of clients in eGovernment, along with the distinction of client and customer.
- S29 Discusses the importance of offshore software development outsourcing (OSDO) in order to develop high quality software at reduced cost.
- S33 Discusses software offshore outsourcing concept and practices in Indian Industry.
- S34 Investigates the client-vendor relationships challenges.
- S35 Presents findings on information technology outsourcing decisions transformation from technical, operational, or procurement decisions, to strategic decisions.
- S37 Investigates eGovernment issues in Nepal.
- S39 Investigates the concept of one of the most important eGovernment barrier; lack of organizational cooperation.
- S40 Discusses the idea of outsourcing in eGovernment initiatives in order to enhance quality.
- S41 Describes the effects/potential benefits of eGovernment that accrue from the use of IT.
- S43 Conducts an in-depth case study evaluation for assessing eProcurement.
- S45 Investigates five major challenges that the eGovernment management faces.
- S47 Presents findings on the importance of eGovernment adoption for success in developing countries.
- S48 Evaluates the public participation in eGovernment using a case from Nepal.
- S49 Discusses the characteristic stages of eGovernment development in terms of world wide web; Web Presence, Interaction,

- Transaction, Transformation.
- S50 Describes the dimensions of eGovernment services, as well as the fundamental needs required for better eGovernment.
- S51 Investigates critical eGovernment benefits to developing countries.
- S52 Discusses the major eGovernment delivery models, such a G2B, G2C,G2G, G2E, and their activities.
- S54 Presents findings on the development of an eGovernment strategy in order to achieve high success rate.
- S57 Investigates and categorizes the challenges in developing countries to be information and data, information technology (IT), organizational and managerial , and legal and regulatory issues, analysis is based on case studies of two eGovernment projects.
- S61 Identifies three paradigms which each include a set of factors that impacts the success of eGovernment success namely, organizational paradigm, technology paradigm and end-users paradigm.
- S62 Discusses the importance of management perspective in order to get success for eGovernment projects.
- S63 Investigates the challenges and benefits of eGovernment initiatives.
- S64 Presents the findings after analyzing the Akshaya project that relationship among stakeholders play important role in eGovernment development.
- S65 Identifies success factors and the Korean eGovernment development stages.
- S66 Analyzes success and failure factors using three different cases, namely: ITPOSMO, ISSM (Information system success Model) and Relation between Administrative discretion and corruption.
- S67 Describes that project management is an integral system approach that must be performed effectively for planning, scheduling, and controlling project activities.
- S70 Identifies 10 success factors for eGovernment projects based on interview data. These are: Funding, IT Infrastructure, Policy and Legal Issues, Awareness, Top Management Support (Political Support), User Computer Efficacy, Reward System, Resistance to Change, Vision & strategy, Training.
- S71 Synthesizes and finds 55 critical eGovernment success factors. Sources of Critical Success Factors (CSFs) are: Communication,
- S72 Top Management Support, Client Acceptance, Project Team Members, Project Change Objective(s), Project Schedule/Plan
- S73 Synthesizes and identifies 36 critical eGovernment success factors. Finds that the creation of sustainable eGovernment development can be assured by increasing collaboration, openness,
- S74 transparency, accountability and participation in government at all levels.

- S75 Observed eGovernment stages, namely: cataloguing, transaction, vertical integration and horizontal integration.
- S76 Describes the factors identified in a survey, that affects adoption of eGovernment services by citizens, namely: performance expectancy, effort expectancy, facilitating conditions and social influence.
- S79 Presents the findings based on the observation and analysis of Saudi Arabian context, issues reported are infrastructure issues, skills and knowledge, security issues, quality of service, awareness issues and culture issues.
- S81 Conclusions are drawn from a survey to measure the impact and effectiveness of eGovernment on the service levels on west coast of Saudi Arabia.
- S93 Covers previous studies and provide help for future in terms of service quality approach to evaluate the web-enabled IT applications.
- S96 The study finds three main purposes of eGovernment use, namely: service use, information use, and policy research.
- S97 Examines some important factors, i.e. digital divide, the nature of the citizen interaction with government, public service values, and satisfaction with services received by citizens.
- S98 Identifies technical, organizational, social, and Financial eGovernment barriers.
- S100 Presents the findings that sustainability plays vital role in eGovernment practices, and helps to achieve continuity and implementing a holistic view of the use of ICT in the public sector.
- S101 The study argues that bureaucracy should be preserved and enhanced where eGovernment policies are to be made.
- S103 Describes the importance of identifying critical success and failure factors, and the processes in order to build a strong relationship.
- S104 Discusses the importance of appropriate policies and evaluates different models working in united nations. The study provides few points to policymakers to develop a deliberately inclusive strategy.
- S105 Presents the findings that traditional government regulation plays an important role and currently is a major governance mode for the eGovernment data protection issue.
- S107 Concludes that user involvement is an integral part of eGovernment success.
- S108 Examines the eGovernment implementation of eXtensible Business Reporting Language (XBRL), and suggests increasing transparency and accountability.
- S109 Describes the importance of benchmarking to remove eGovernment issues.
- S112 Describes the policy level, organizational level, technological level issues in eGovernment.

	S115	Discusses the obstacles, the strategy for improvements, and achievements made in Jordanian eGovernment.
	S116	Using e-stamping service in Hong Kong as a case study, the study examines the impact of leadership and stakeholders on the success or failure of eGovernment service in Hong Kong.
	S118	The findings show that in implementing OPEN, a system for anti-corruption, the regulatory dimension was most effective, and strong leadership was crucial to its success.
	S119	Describes that eGovernment policies should focus not only on the technical aspects of information exchange infrastructures, but on the collaboration as well.
	S121	Addresses different institutional and cultural contexts which must be considered when implementing eGovernment in sub-Saharan Africa.
	S127	Investigates the scope using interviews and describes that major problems that eGovernment professionals face are organizational, technical, and human resource issues.
	S129	Presents the findings that leaders are openly deploying eGovernment applications to improve administrative improvements. It can be done if concerns transform government functions, reform procedures, and enhance transparency. Analysis was made using China's eGovernment as a case.
	S131	Presents the findings of importance of two stage model, incorporating G2C, G2G and G2B relationships.
Framework	S7	Architecture framework for eGovernment adoption that can help to guide IT managers recognize the technological and organizational requirements.
	S13	Framework for pursuing the influence of research on the public managers' practices by using practical guides.
	S15	A descriptive framework incorporating input, output variables and the action plan for success.
	S23	The analytical framework that have some external factors and a number of internal factors which combine and give outcome (Performance).
	S31	The framework groups factors affecting network performance into three categories: network structure, institutional forces, and technology.
	S32	A framework of comprehensive offshoring challenges and solutions for the theoretical and practice domains.
	S36	A general framework for better planning and monitoring mechanisms in eGovernment initiative.
	S38	A theoretical framework built on two elements: structuration theory and the literature on organizational IS assimilation.
	S42	A comprehensive framework for using critical success factors.
	S44	A framework to better understand the related, dependent, determined, specific, and ethical & policy issues.
	S46	A framework incorporating literacy concept in order to achieve

		success at all levels of eGovernment.
	S55	The conceptual framework for eGovernment implementation proposed; incorporating network Access, network learning, network economy, network policy, and culture and society factors.
	S56	A basic framework that address eGovernment's definition, characteristics and types.
	S58	A framework for improving eGovernment by including technologies such as Open Source and Cloud Computing.
	S69	A framework to build on current theory development and practice in eGovernment initiative.
	S83	Adoption and Utilization framework was proposed showing the factors that have influence on adoption of eGovernment.
	S88	A research framework which give better guidance on future research regarding the managerial level implementation, in order to achieve a collaborative and agile management approach in eGovernment.
	S94	Framework for analyzing different countries' eGovernment initiatives.
	S95	A framework that provide evidence of black-box status for some eGovernment functions and institutionalization.
	S102	A theoretical framework for eGovernment innovation.
	S110	A theoretical framework to guide on the procedure of looking for government information online.
	S113	A conceptual framework to understand eGovernment planning and implementation.
	S124	A framework mapping eGovernment main goals to two important factors; eGovernment readiness degree and the democratization level.
Model	S5	Four-stage model having levels of integration is proposed. The stages are :(1) cataloguing, (2) transaction, (3) vertical integration, and (4) horizontal integration.
	S12	A model and topology for stakeholder roles and stakeholder benefits proposed, which can be used to map stakeholder roles to stakeholder benefits.
	S14	The conceptual model proposed describing few factors that are critical for any eGovernment success or failure.
	S16	Proposed an integrated theoretical model i.e. United Theory of Acceptance and Use of Technology (UTUAT), having five major elements of behavioural intention and use behaviour: performance expectancy, effort expectancy, peer influence, facilitating conditions, and internet experience.
	S19	A model for design-reality gap understanding.
	S30	A model for understanding service quality, relationship quality and user satisfaction.
	S60	A conceptual model of change management in eGovernment implementation.

	S78	The model using UTAUT variables and finds Performance Expectancy, Effort Expectancy and Social Influence as having positive affect.
	S90	A conceptual model giving clear view on acceptance of internet services by the users
	S92	A theoretical model to analyze eGovernment studies and used bibliometric analysis for examination of constructs, i.e. theoretical perspectives, methods, and units of analysis.
	S99	A novel model egovDR is proposed, consisting of three principles, policy principle, co-design principle, and theorizing principle.
	S106	A triangle model of eGovernment adoption drivers and public value production that re-elaborate combining the elements, concepts, and theories reviewed in the literature.
	S117	A new model build on the basis of 'technology enactment framework,' in conjunction with the 'systems development life cycle' approach.
	S120	A multidisciplinary model for eGovernment project planning.
	S128	A novel model named Public Sector Process Rebuilding (PPR) maturity model for eGovernment success. It is an extension of the Layne and Lee model.
	S130	A testable model that outline the cost, complexity, and potential performance of eGovernment initiatives.
	S132	A generic model to develop and implement successful eGovernment.
Recommendations	S20	Recommendations for IT strategic planning.
	S53	Recommendations for developing strategies to align stakeholders' interests so that participation in eGovernment can be self-Governing.
	S77	Recommends increasing accountability and involvement at all levels of eGovernment services.
	S80	Briefs to reduce failure rate by understanding issues.
	S82	Recommends adding engage stakeholders in order to achieve success.
	S87	The use of UTAUT model variables effectively can enhance the development and implementation of eGovernment projects.
	S89	Suggest ways of strengthening eGovernment research.
	S91	Recommends ways of improvement in terms of costs and infrastructure, training, technical, managerial and legal factors.
	S111	Suggests that eGovernment initiatives need to play significant role for corruption control and poverty reduction.
	S123	Recommend addressing the socio-economic context and needs of the country, i.e. financial and human resources, and user satisfaction.

Table 13

Research approach facets		
Research approach	Studies(S)	# of studies
Evaluation Research	S2, S3, S15, S18, S21, S26, S27, S29, S33, S34, S37, S40, S42, S43, S47, S48, S53, S57, S61, S62, S64, S65, S66, S72, S73, S74, S75, S79, S82, S92, S96, S97, S100, S101, S104, S105, S108, S112, S115, S116, S118, S121, S127, S129, S131	45
Experience Paper	S1, S6, S25, S50	4
Opinion Paper	S4, S8, S9, S10, S11, S17, S20, S22, S24, S28, S35, S39, S41, S45, S49, S51, S52, S54, S56, S63, S67, S70, S71, S76, S80, S81, S84, S91, S93, S98, S103, S107, S109, S111, S114, S119, S122, S123, S125, S126	40
Philosophical Paper	S7, S13, S16, S23, S31, S32, S36, S38, S44, S46, S55, S58, S59, S68, S69, S83, S87, S88, S89, S94, S102, S110, S113, S117, S124	25
Solution Proposal	S5, S12, S14, S19, S30, S60, S77, S78, S85, S86, S90, S95, S99, S106, S120, S128, S130, S132	18

5.5. Object involved in the study and research context

Sub-RQ2: What type of study setting were used by these studies to investigate their required information?

The study settings for these selected studies comprise of industrial, academic, and the mixed setting (some part of the research is done for academic purpose, and some part has been done from industry). The studies under the category of adoption (8 studies), twenty five (25) studies under development, seventeen (17) studies under implementation, four (4) studies under infrastructure and nine (9) studies under management category, and

only one (1) study under stakeholder participation category had their assessment done in real world case. The rest of the settings include four (4) from the academic setting in adoption, nineteen (19) studies belong to academic and four (4) to mixed setting under development, fifteen (15) to academic and three (3) to mixed under implementation, three (3) to academic and two (2) to mixed under infrastructure, eight (8) to academic and three (3) to mixed under management, and four (4) to academic and three (3) to mixed under stakeholder category. Table 15 shows the study settings involved in each study

Table 14:-

Research method used		
Research Method	Studies(S)	# of studies
Exploratory Research	S2, S4, S5, S7, S11, S12, S13, S14, S16, S17, S19, S21, S23, S29, S31, S32, S36, S38, S39, S42, S44, S46, S49, S51, S58, S59, S60, S63, S65, S68, S69, S70, S74, S77, S83, S84, S86, S87, S88, S89, S90, S92, S93, S94, S98, S103, S104, S106, S109, S111, S113, S115, S119, S121, S123, S124, S125, S127, S128, S129, S130, S132	62
Case Study	S3, S27, S33, S34, S37, S40, S43, S47, S48, S53, S55, S57, S61, S62, S64, S66, S75, S79, S95, S99, S100, S101, S102, S105, S107,	33

S108, S112, S116, S117, S118, S120, S122, S126

Survey	S20, S25, S30, S67, S72, S76, S78, S80, S81, S82, S85, S91, S96, S97, S110, S114, S131	17
Experience Report	S6, S50	2
Action Research	S1	1
Meta-Ethnography	S71, S73	2
Observational Study	S8, S9, S10, S15, S18, S22, S24, S26, S28, S35, S41, S45, S52, S54, S56	15

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Table 15:-

Study setting in each study

Category	Studies (S)	Setting	# of studies
Adoption	S1, S37, S47, S76, S78, S79, S83, S102	Industrial	8
	S7, S16, S87, S106	Academic	4
Development	S3, S5, S9, S13, S19, S22, S30, S33, S39, S50, S54, S57, S61, S64, S73, S75, S97, S99, S100, S101, S105, S107, S116, S120, S131	Industrial	25
	S2, S24, S29, S40, S44, S49, S52, S56, S66, S74, S86, S89, S92, S109, S111, S123, S124, S128, S129	Academic	19
	S6, S34, S65, S93	Mixed	4
	S4, S43, S48, S51, S62, S70, S80, S82, S85, S95, S98, S108, S112, S117, S118, S122, S126	Industrial	17
Implementation	S8, S11, S36, S41, S58, S71, S84, S103, S104, S113, S114, S115, S121, S125, S132	Academic	15
	S14, S15, S55	Mixed	3
Infrastructure	S20, S25, S81, S96	Industrial	4
	S26, S31, S119	Academic	3

	S42, S63	Mixed	2
Management	S18, S21, S23, S27, S35, S46, S67, S72, S88	Industrial	9
	S17, S45, S60, S68, S69, S94, S127, S130	Academic	8
	S10, S38, S59	Mixed	3
Stakeholder	S53	Industrial	1
Participation/Importance	S12, S28, S77, S110	Academic	4
	S32, S90, S91	Mixed	3

5.2. Publication for a

Sub-RQ3: Which publication fora included studies on eGovernment aspects?

Tables 16, 17 and 18 display the list of journals, conferences, societies and workshop for all included studies respectively. Among the 132 studies, 107 were from journals, 14 from conferences, 10 from societies and 1 from a workshop. The data show that research on eGovernment and its importance appears in diverse journals, and few conferences, societies and workshop as well.

List of journals		
Studies(S)	Journal Name	# of studies
S2	Journal of Business Systems, Governance and Ethics	1
S3, S5, S8, S11, S13, S88, S89, S90, S91, S92, S93, S94, S95, S96, S97, S99, S100, S101, S102, S103, S104, S105, S106, S107, S108, S109, S110, S111, S112, S113, S114, S115, S116, S117, S118, S119, S120, S121, S122, S123, S124, S125, S126, S127, S128, S129, S130, S131	Government Information Quarterly 	48
S4	Electronic Journal Information Systems Evaluation	1
S7	Business Process Management Journal	1
S10, S26, S43	The Electronic Journal on Information Systems in Developing Countries	3
S12	International Journal of Information Management	1
S15, S44, S45, S46, S47, S48	Electronic Journal of e-Government	6
S16, S22	IEEE	2
S17	Journal of Research and Innovation in Information Systems	1
S18, S24	Information Technology for Development	2
S19	The Information Society	1
S20	Pakistan Journal of Social Sciences (PJSS)	1
S23	Journal of Public Performance & Management Review	1

S27	International Journal of Business and Social Science	1
S30	Journal of Computer Information Systems	1
S32	Information Systems Management	1
S35	Journal of Management Information Systems	1
S36	European Journal of Scientific Research	1
S37, S56	International Journal of the Computer, the Internet and Management	2
S38	Electronic Commerce Research and Applications	1
S40	Journal of Outsourcing & Organizational Information Management	1
S42	Information and Security, an International Journal	1
S51	Journal of Software Engineering and Applications	1
S52	Interscience Management Review	1
S53, S55	Journal of Global Information Management	2
S58, S71	International Journal of Computer Applications	2
S60	Journal of Business Systems Research	1
S63	International Journal of Humanities and Social Science	1
S66	Egyptian Informatics Journal	1
S67	Journal of Inspiration Economy	1
S69	International Journal of Project Management	1
S72	Journal of Social and Development Sciences	1
S73	Research Journal of Applied Sciences, Engineering and Technology	1
S74	A Research Journal of South Asian Studies	1
S75	International Journal of Computer Science Issues	1
S76	Journal of Theoretical and Applied Information Technology	1
S77	Journal of Electronics and Communication Engineering	1
S78	International Journal of Scientific & Technology Research	1
S79, S83, S87	International Journal of Advanced Computer Science and Applications	3
S80	International Journal for Infonomics	1
S81	BVICAM's International Journal of Information Technology	1
S82	International Journal of Applied Information Systems	1
S84	International Business Management	1
S85	International Journal of Network Security	1
S86	Journal of Socialomics	1
S132	Journal of King Saud University - Computer and Information Sciences	1

Table 17:-

List of conferences

Studies(S)	Conference Name	# of studies
S1	Proceedings of SIG GlobDev Third Annual Workshop, Saint Louis	1
S6	European Conference on eGovernment	1
S9	CMG Italy, XIX Annual Conference	1
S14	European and Mediterranean Conference on Information Systems	1
S25	Proceedings of 2nd European conference on Mobile Government, Mobile Government Consortium International (2006)	1
S29	International Symposium on Research in Innovation and Sustainability	1
S31	National Public Management Research Conference	1
S39, S57, S64	European Conference on Information Systems	3
S61	European, Mediterranean & Middle Eastern Conference on Information Systems	1
S62	International conference on Electronic government	1
S70	International Conference on Computing and Informatics	1
S98	Proceedings of the IASK International Conference E-Activity and Leading Technologies & InterTIC 2010	1

Table 18:-
List of workshop and society

Studies(S)	Journal Name	Type	# of studies
S19	The Information Society	society	1
S21	Institute for Development Policy and Management	society	1
S28	Pre-ECIS workshop on E-government	workshop	1
S32	Information Systems Management	society	1
S33	University of Hertfordshire Society	society	1
S38	Electronic Commerce Research and Applications	society	1
S41	International Association for Computer Information Systems	society	1
S49	Information Polity Press	society	1
S50	New York City Council Select Committee	society	1
S52	Interscience Management Review	society	1
S54	Department of Telecommunications & Information Services	society	1

5.3. Suggested areas for further research

This section describes the possible research areas that need additional investigation in future on the basis of our mapping study. These research gaps suggested below are considered on the basis of

classification scheme used in our mapping study, and on the data interpretation and the number of studies found in each area.

- **Development: We suggest four (4) further research purposes in this category:**

(i) **Assigning proper roles:** among the 132 papers included in this mapping study, least studies (S6, S107, S116, S128) had a little attention was given to this important subject. These studies have conversed about its importance very convincingly. However, more research and investigation is required for this sub-topic.

(ii) **Social issues' critical factors:** few studies have abstractly talked about social issues; however, detailed factors that come under this sub-topic are still unknown to most of the eGovernment developers. Therefore, we recommend conducting an in-depth study that encompasses list of maximum number of social factors.

(iii) **Participatory studies:** there were five (5) participatory studies in total, i.e. experience report (2; S6, S50) meta-ethnography (2; S71, S73) and action research (1; S1). Heeks (2002) highlights that studies in which researchers are involved is an area that requires further investigation. Therefore, more participatory studies are required under this category.

(iv) **Real world contexts:** we consider that eGovernment initiative procedures, models and frameworks might be better assessed using real world cases and projects. As these models and frameworks are developed for improvement, therefore these must be assessed in real-world projects in order to develop a convincing opinion.

• **Metrics:** a less number of studies were concerned with metrics for eGovernment aspects. Therefore, we consider it as a research gap.

• **Integrative studies:** we found that less focus has been given to the integrative studies. Therefore, we suggest that highly integrative research studies must be performed in the eGovernment domain.

6. Discussion

This systematic mapping study aimed to construct a classification scheme, and to collect, comprehend and analyze related evidence for eGovernment major aspects and focus areas. To the best of our knowledge, no convincing and comprehensive systematic mapping studies in this significant and continuously evolving field are available currently. Therefore, a thorough, methodical and unbiased systematic mapping study can be a great contribution to the body of knowledge of eGovernment studies.

This mapping study specifies a number of research gaps that need attention and further investigation and research. First, the studies that were classified under adoption and infrastructure categories identify challenges, and discuss on the other focus areas, consequently offering analysis based on literature. If these studies, on the other hand, were conducted using information from *real development settings*, and afterwards assessed their analysis or conclusions in such settings, the importance of these studies would have been more considerable and complete. Therefore, it is highly recommended that evaluation of eGovernment frameworks and models should be applied on complex systems such as security and critical systems. Further, the studies were not based on real-world development requirements.

Secondly, there is a deficiency of studies addressing the focus area "roles in eGovernment". As discussed in Section 6.7, only four studies (S6, S107, S116, S128) provided slight awareness in this focus area. Furthermore, it is important to note that leaders in eGovernment projects should develop a sense of assigning roles and responsibilities early during planning phase [S128]. The developers should also be aware of the roles so that they can work appropriately.

To elaborate more, there are no other empirical studies addressing eGovernment aspects and their focus areas so rigorously. eGovernment initiatives are currently considered the backbone of any country, therefore, requires high availability, accountability and reliability of such initiatives. Additionally, there is very little number of studies offering experience reports for eGovernment domain.

Further, and as revealed in Section 6.7, fewer studies have used participatory method for data

collection and analysis. Consequently, a lot of more research can be done using participatory methods in this evolving domain to provide better results.

Finally, on the basis of our observation that most studies applied evaluation research approach, we consider that eGovernment project developer would find it problematic to select among the most suitable contribution for their projects. This is due to the fact that several frameworks, models and recommendations have been provided by these selected studies, but the developers have no clear road-map for guidance. We suggest future studies that can provide an evaluation and help to guide eGovernment professionals for real-world projects.

6.1. Threats to validity

A number of factors need to be considered for generalized results in this mapping study. Initially, only electronically available articles were considered during the process of identifying relevant literature. However, this might have neglected some important studies that could have been part of conference proceedings or journals that were not available online. But since the eGovernment domain is to some extent new (earliest paper was published in 2000), we consider that it is not likely that relevant studies are not easy to access.

Some additional major threats to the results' validity relate to bias in selecting relevant studies and extracting inaccurate data. We tried a number of search strings to select the most suitable search string. However, we cannot assure that we got all appropriate studies; moreover, there would have been a chance that some studies were missed due to search terms. However, we conducted piloting of the search terms choice and it might assist to reduce the risk of omitting important data.

We included the empirical studies only in our study. Our reasoning was that studies having a empirical element deliver some level of in-depth analysis of the advantages and restrictions of the eGovernment aspect discussed.

The procedure of extracting the data might have been obstructed by biasness while studies' selection. It is primarily because the data was extracted by one researcher (first author). The second author selected 10% of the selected studies randomly and worked on the extraction on his own, for validation of data

extraction. Then, we compared and discussed results in a meeting, and checked that there were any inconsistencies, and continued till we reach a consensus.

The classification scheme structure could have influenced the results' presentation. The classification scheme developed in this mapping study comprise of four main categories (i.e. structure of the theme/topic/aspect, contribution facets, study setting, and the research facet). Such classification was developed using guidelines given by Petersen et al., (2008), and this could have possibly neglected the examination of some additional related attributes that would have been in the primary studies.

7. Conclusions and future research

On the basis of the outcomes of our systematic mapping study, we offer an analysis (review) of the state of knowledge of qualitative papers in the eGovernment domain. A total of 7104 studies from six online databases was examined and passed through three filtration stages. A total of 132 studies was finally included and mapped to the classification scheme, on the basis of the defined inclusion/exclusion criteria. Our classification scheme included four categories: first: the major classification to structure the aspect and contains adoption, development, implementation, management, infrastructure and stakeholders' participation/importance sub-categories. These sub-categories depict the main subject addressed by the study. Then for each topic (sub-category), the main focus areas (identified by the authors) addressed by respective studies were reflected concisely. Second category: signifies the contribution facet, i.e. framework, model, metrics, recommendation and evaluation. The third category refers to objects/setting involved, as a study is done in a simple academic setting or any real world industrial project has been assessed. The fourth classification signifies the research approaches or research facet used in the paper. These comprise of evaluation research, experience paper, opinion paper, philosophical paper and solution proposal.

A lot of research gaps have been identified, defined in section 7. First, the studies in the adoption and infrastructure categories, few studies have used real-world environments. Secondly, the studies on

eGovernment roles are deficient. Additionally, there is very little number of studies offering experience reports for eGovernment domain. It is also reported that practitioners will find it challenging to select appropriate model or framework and that it necessitates a clear road-map for their guidance. Our future work will encompass study addressing real-world eGovernment challenges that professionals face. Accordingly, a framework will be developed that will incorporate potential solutions that can help to address identified research gaps

8. Research limitations

As in any systematic mapping study, a number of considerations can limit the reliability of drawn conclusions. Here, the most important one has been conversed; "Selection Bias": The key limitation of this paper is that papers having weak abstract were not included. The quantitative studies were excluded. The purpose was to contribute a big picture of qualitative studies. Another limitation while selecting papers was the logical rejection of very short papers, assuming that fewer pages do not state appropriate results.

Appendix A

The included studies list is provided The references listed below correspond to those introduced with the letter "S" in the paper.

- | | | | |
|----|--|-----|---|
| S1 | Gregor, S., Imran, A., & Turner, T. (2010). Designing for a "Sweet Spot" in an Intervention in a Least Developed Country: The Case of e-Government in Bangladesh. Proceedings of SIG GlobDev Third Annual Workshop, Saint Louis, USA | S5 | Layne, K., & Lee, J. (2001). Developing fully functional E-government: A four stage model. Government Information Quarterly, 18(2), 122-136 |
| S2 | Gregor, S., & Imran, A. (2005). A comparative analysis of strategies for E-Government in developing countries. Journal of Business Systems, Governance and Ethics, 2(3), 89-99 | S6 | Noor, M., Khan, M., Khan, A., & Brekhna (2014). Vendors' challenges in e-Government Projects in Pakistan: Experience Report of Prisons Automation. European Conference on eGovernment, 189-197. |
| S3 | Anna, Y., & Kei, A. (2005). Challenges in E-Government development: Lessons from two Information Kiosk Projects. Government Information Quarterly, 22(1), 58-74 | S7 | Ebrahim, Z., & Irani, Z. (2005). E-government adoption: architecture and barriers. Business Process Management Journal, 11(5), 589-611 |
| S4 | Matavire, R., Chigona, W., Roode, D., Sewchurran, E., Davids, Z., Mukudu, A., & Boamah-Abu, C. C. (2010). Challenges of E-Government Project Implementation in a | S8 | Paul, T., & Thompson, K. (2003). E-government around the world: Lessons, challenges, and future directions. Government Information Quarterly, 20(3), 389-394 |
| | | S9 | Signore, O., Chessi, F., & Palotti, M. (2005). E-Government: Challenges and Opportunities. Computer Measurement Group (CMG) Italy, XIX Conference. Italy, 1-16 |
| | | S10 | Ndou, V. (2004). E-Government for developing countries: Opportunities and Challenges. Electronic Journal on Information Systems in Developing Countries (EJISDC), 18(1), 1-24. |
| | | S11 | Yildiz, M. (2007). E-Government research: Reviewing the Literature, limitations and ways forward. Government Information Quarterly, 24(3), 646-665. |
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| | | S14 | Al-Rashidi, H. (2010). Examining Internal Challenges to E-Government Implementation from System Users Perspective. European and Mediterranean |

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